

EBFMC25-OP-52 · Emotional Manipulation in Married Individuals: Marital Attitudes and Family Belonging

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Marriage is an institution in which individuals are connected by emotional, social, and cultural bonds, based on mutual understanding, respect, and trust. However, some individuals may resort to negative communication patterns, such as emotional manipulation, in an attempt to gain power and control within the relationship. Emotional manipulation is a major risk factor that undermines trust between partners, threatens psychological integrity, and reduces relational satisfaction. This study examines the effects of emotional manipulation on marital attitudes and family belonging in married individuals, in light of theoretical and empirical findings.

Materials and Methods: This study primarily involved a literature review focused on the relationship between emotional manipulation, marital attitudes, and family belonging among married individuals.

Results: Emotional manipulation is defined as an attempt to control another person by triggering feelings such as guilt, fear, shame, or dependency (Simon, 1996). Manipulative tactics include patterns such as gaslighting (distortion of reality), silent treatment, passive-aggressive behaviors, and excessive jealousy. Marital attitude reflects an individual's thoughts, emotions, and behavioral tendencies regarding marriage. Positive marital attitudes are characterized by respect for the spouse, belief in the sanctity of marriage, and high motivation toward maintaining the relationship (Yıldırım & Demirtaş, 2013). In manipulative relationships, these positive attitudes may weaken over time, potentially leading to emotional alienation. Family belonging encompasses an individual's sense of attachment, feeling of belonging, and awareness of responsibility toward their family. While a strong sense of belonging is typical in healthy relationships, in relationships where manipulation is intense, individuals may experience emotional distancing from the family environment, alienation, or a sense of burnout (Çiftçi & Arkan, 2020). Various studies have shown that emotional manipulation in marriage negatively affects individuals' attitudes toward the marital relationship. For instance, a study by Karaca and Güngör (2018) indicated that manipulative behaviors decrease marital satisfaction and contribute to emotional detachment between spouses.

Conclusion: Emotional manipulation is a serious communication problem that should not be overlooked in marital relationships. Individuals exposed to manipulative behavior tend to develop negative marital attitudes, experience a reduced sense of belonging, and report lower life satisfaction. Therefore, it is crucial for couples to increase their emotional awareness, develop healthy communication skills, and seek psychological counseling when necessary. Additionally, incorporating discussions on healthy relationship dynamics and types of manipulation into premarital education programs may help prevent potential risks.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Emotional manipulation, family belonging, marital attitude

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is an institution in which individuals are bound by emotional, social, and cultural ties; it is based on mutual understanding, respect, and trust. In this context, marital attitudes and family belonging are important indicators reflecting individuals' expectations from marriage, their roles in the relationship, and their commitment to family structure. However, some individuals may resort to negative communication patterns such as emotional manipulation to gain power and control in the relationship. Emotional manipulation is a significant risk factor that undermines trust between spouses, threatens psychological integrity, and decreases relational satisfaction. This study examines the effects of emotional manipulation on marital attitudes and family belonging among married individuals, in light of theoretical and empirical findings.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was constructed by analyzing five master's theses and twenty-two national and international academic publications from the years 2010–2025, selected retrospectively, focusing on the relationship between family belonging and marital attitudes among married individuals.

RESULTS

Emotional manipulation is defined as an attempt by an individual to control the other person by triggering emotions such as guilt, fear, shame, or dependency (Simon, 1996). Manipulative tactics include gaslighting (distorting reality), silent treatment, passive-aggressive behaviors, and extreme jealousy. Such behaviors in marital relationships damage trust and reduce the quality of communication between spouses. Marital attitude refers to an individual's tendencies in thoughts, feelings, and behaviors regarding marriage. Positive marital attitudes are characterized by respect for the spouse, belief in the sanctity of marriage, and high motivation toward the relationship (Yıldırım & Demirtaş, 2013). In manipulative relationships, these positive attitudes may weaken over time, leading to alienation in the relationship.

Family belonging encompasses a sense of loyalty, belongingness, and responsibility toward one's family. In healthy relationships, this sense is strong, whereas in relationships with intense manipulation, individuals may experience emotional distancing, alienation, or burnout within the family context (Çiftçi & Arkan, 2020). Various studies show that emotional manipulation in marriage negatively affects individuals' marital attitudes. For example, in a study by Karaca and Güngör (2018), manipulative behaviors were found to reduce marital satisfaction and cause emotional detachment between spouses. It was also revealed that individuals continuously subjected to manipulation become alienated from their family roles and experience weakened family belonging.

CONCLUSION

Emotional manipulation is a serious communication issue in marital relationships that should not be overlooked. Individuals exposed to manipulative behaviors exhibit negative marital attitudes, weakened sense of belonging, and decreased overall life satisfaction. Therefore, it is essential for couples to increase their emotional awareness, acquire healthy communication skills, and seek psychological counseling when necessary. Additionally, addressing healthy relationship dynamics and types of manipulation in pre-marital education programs may help prevent potential risks.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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